

POET RECOGNIZED BY ALL LITERARY LOVERS OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7162538>

Annotation: This article describes Alexander Feinberg's thoughts, parts of his life, and some of his work. The golden thoughts of Uzbek writers about the Russian poet and his immortal works became the decoration of the article. Some examples from Feinberg's works are provided, as well as their definition and purpose of writing. It is told about the Russian poet who was born and grew up in Uzbekistan, worked shoulder-to-shoulder with the people of this country throughout his life, and made a great contribution to the development of the country.

Key words: Alexander Feinberg, immortal works, Uzbek, Abdulla Aripov, freedom, Republic of Uzbekistan, David, poet, Kandahar, culture, Tashkent, poetry, collections, screenwriter, film scripts.

The well-known Uzbek poet Abdulla Aripov said, "As for the work of Alexander Feinberg, all the stories do not reflect a hundredth of the truth, because he was actually an unworthy poet and translator. "None of the world's Russian-speaking writers can sing sincere songs to our sunny land." described it as.

In fact, his immortal works are not only in the hands of Uzbeks, but also in the hearts of poetry lovers all over the world. Poetry collections are in everyone's hands. Even after the poet's death, translations are being carried out by his fans. Due to his long-term work, loyalty, and strong love for his homeland, holidays and events are organized in Uzbekistan every year in his memory of the poet.

It is known to everyone that Feinberg's childhood was full of hardships, that is, dark clouds hovered over the heads of Uzbeks. He described this in many of his poems. As an example, we can cite the poem "Tashkent," written in 1943, about how terrible it was during the war years.

Above David the Shoemaker's Workshop

A newspaper kite hung from the wires.

Heat. Along the stone pavement

Knocks to the beer wheelchair invalid.

Six months since Aunt Lida went crazy.

waiting for letters from dead sons.

The old man snores at her door,

Looking at the tattered mantle.

Slow summer floats on the rear.

The Father of Nations squints at the portrait.
Beneath it is a closed bakery shop.

Green house. Shelter of love and faith.

Ranevskaya mined kerosene.

Akhmatova opens doors.

Due to his non-standard behavior, the poet's opportunity to publish seven years' worth of poetry in one day was closed, and this situation encouraged him to create film scripts. Screenwriting was an important part of Feinberg's work. A total of four feature films and twenty animated films were shot. Based on his script, the films "Under the Narrow Sun", "My Brother", and "Healed in Kandahar" were shot at the "Uzbekfilm" film studio. In "Criminals and acquittals" and a number of other films in the "Tajikfilm" film studio. He is also the author of more than twenty cartoons.

Hope is enough for me.

And the grave is not the end of the road...

Alexander Feinberg, paraphrasing the above verses, declares that he will not back down, even after the hardships he has experienced throughout his life. The poet hopes that after dark and difficult days, bright, that is, good days will come. Their hopes and patience have come true, and with the will of God Almighty and the movement of patriots, good days have arrived, that is, the blessings of freedom. At the end of his life, although he could not fully feel this blessing, he tasted it and was relieved at least a little from his joy.

By reading Feinberg's books, poems, and thoughts, one's worldview is broadened and one is also encouraged to move forward in life. The following poem also reveals Feinberg's inner world and is worth emulating.

And still I can't understand.

Why do I need this fucking fate-to be happy,
at the same time tormented,
to know this life of begging and treasure?

Hello, stranger. Hello to everyone.

None of us have been taught for centuries—
neither a clear sun, nor a falling star—
where to go, where to find the answer.

Alexander Arkadyevich Feinberg's eternal dream and the most important factor that decided his happiness was not only the peace of the country, but also the safety of our planet. Even though the talented poet was not physically like the

soldiers in the war, he worked diligently for the welfare of the country and contributed to raising the morale of the people. Feinberg made a great contribution to the development of multinational Uzbek literature and was recognized by the government. The fact that he was awarded the honorary titles of "Honored Cultural Worker of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" is a proof of our boundless respect for this great man.

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